

Interview MAE / Agathe Riquier
13.12.21 1h

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Updated: 2021-07-28

WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

Short description of the institution :

The Musée de l'Air et de l'Espace (MAE) is a museum about « everything relating to aviation, from social, cultural, economic and anthropological point of view. The 'technical' label attached to the museum consequently seems to be very restrictive, but this restrictive view was nonetheless the one that prevailed for a long time »¹.

Collections date back to the 18th century, and include 400 aircrafts but also a large collection of iconographic documents (24 000 references), artworks (eg., sculptures, paintings) and objects (eg., memorabilia, uniforms).

• The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project ? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection ? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach ? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

Only one example of wreck fitting with Procraft perspective, wreck of Antoine de Saint-Exupery (see associated form A). Wreck is understood in the aerchaological sense here = from recovery/excavation, maritime context (Mediterranee).

2 other wrecks in the collections, but out of Procraft's scope : Normandie-Niemen (from a lake) and Ariane (maritime).

MAE not normally involved in the recovery or systematic preservation of wrecks. No particular interest in WWII wrecks. Has not been involved in the recovery of this wreck either.

St-Exupery wreck has been recovered for the Mediterreanean in 2003, by group of archeologist and fisherman (who had found the wreck). Belongs to the DRASSM, has been given in long term deposition to the MAE in 2005. Wreck composed of 80 fragments and parts.

No clear information how the decision was made to deposit in this museum preferably to another. Maybe related to the size and number of fragments, or to the association with a prestigious historical figure.

¹ Sourced on line :

Clémence Raynaud, « Un musée technique, d'histoire et de société : l'apport des collections iconographiques du musée de l'Air et de l'Espace », In Situ [En ligne], 35 | 2018, mis en ligne le 29 août 2018, consulté le 13 décembre 2021. URL : <http://journals.openedition.org/insitu/16851> ; DOI : <https://doi.org/10.4000/insitu.16851>

- Concept of “conservation” : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle ? How do you define long term ? What does the idea of “conservation” mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

The general approach has gradually changed in the last 10-15 years, moving from aeronautical maintenance type of interventions to treatment decisions more respectful of the original materials of the objects/aircrafts.

Today in general, and the St- Exupery parts, mainly active conservation, aiming at stabilization of corrosion.

Also presentation of the fragments and parts as they are, there is no will nor possibility to recreate a complete aircraft. Also wish to show the history of the wreck : marine concretions left in place, Piece of fishing net still on the train leg.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

On this artefact : no treatment since arrival at the museum until 2019-2020. Only one workshop by conservation students in 2013, but just study and condition assesement.

At the MAE : treatments carried out by a trained conservator (graduated from La Sorbonne) in collaboration with the collection manager and scientists (C2RMF and Institut Jean Lamour) for the developpement of treatment protocole with carboxylates.

During recovery : archives and scarce documentation show that treatments have been carried out by member of th team in situ (a coppersmith, archaeologist) Acid baths (no metion of concentration, rinsing and repetition), mechanical removal of concretions (tool marks still visible), high level of polish on certain parts.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

Wreck is only parts and fragments, not in use conditions. Not recongnizable as a complete aircraft, only certain parts can be visually identified.

Fragments have been in storage for most of the time since arrived at the MAE in 2005.

Some fragments have been part of an exhibition in ???

Today some of the parts and fragments are part of a new touring exhibition, started in 2020 in Lyon, and getting back at the MAE in 2024.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

Currently and since 2007, fragments have been stored in a non climatized storage. Important HR and T variation during the year.

Awareness of consequences on the long-term preservation, but lack of space in better equipped storage facility. Visible changes of condition on photos taken at different periods, particularly for the turbo, who is very powdery and crumbles to dust.

Plan to move fragments and parts in a climatized storage, after clearing some space. No set date yet, as soon as possible.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

Main issues with the St-Exupery parts are Al corrosion ; also Fe, but less important. Synthetic materials in relative good condition.

Al corrosion, variable in type and intensity depending on the fragments and the alloys (see form A for characteristics of the fragments included in Procraft).

Observed type of corrosion overall : blue-green corrosion products with lace appearance of certain parts, exfoliation corrosion, galvanic corrosion, pulverulence and spalling. On some parts, visible influence of high temperature near the element during use or crash.

In general, corrosion of Al alloys is an important issue at the MAE, as the material is very commonly encountered in the collections. Similar types of corrosion are for ex. observed on the Ariane wreck.

Treatment on some of the parts carried out with carboxylates. No details available about this treatment, see future publication. On if the issues encountered with this type of treatment is the change of surface appearance, as it changes to a black appearance.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

Changes initiated in the recent years.

On the St- Exupery, archival search to document as much as possible what happened during and shortly the recovery.

Many issues between the various stakeholders (internal and external to the museum) around this project, at various stages. Actions in spurts so far.

Particular interest in knowing more about treatment of Al corrosion, cleaning, stabilization. Treatment with carboxylates not always possible since it changes surface colour and appearance.

Also interest for preventive conservation recommendations, in particular as the MAE has special conditions : no possible regulation of environment in the exhibition spaces (either historical buildings or warehouses), very close to Le Bourget airport, so exposed to a lot of heavy pollution.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

St-Exupery wreck has value by its connection of a significant French historical figure, and presented as such, more like a relic. Aircraft itself is nothing special as it was mass produced and well documented otherwise. Also influence of the Fondation St-Exupery, who is eager to promote St-Exupery heritage as much as possible, including for financial benefits.

Exhibit at the museum a few years ago with the train leg.

Currently fragments in two exhibits, one of which will be touring and coming back to the MAE in 2024.